

Entrepreneurship Education in Côte d'Ivoire

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Abstract: This article deals with entrepreneurship education in Côte d'Ivoire. Entrepreneurship is in fact, in Côte d'Ivoire, an alternative to overcome employment and unemployment problems. The objective of this study is to show that entrepreneurship education in Ivorian establishments is of capital importance in the face of the challenges of the present century. An analysis of entrepreneurship education in Côte d'Ivoire is also the subject of the discussion. In this document, the importance of entrepreneurship education, the challenges it faces and the solutions for the Ivorian government and for decision-makers who can serve as databases for decision-making were also discussed. This article also addresses the relationship between entrepreneurship training and the performance of SMEs in Côte d'Ivoire. As part of this documentary study, various research documents related to entrepreneurship education and theories were examined. This study is an important contribution to the literature on entrepreneurship education in Côte d'Ivoire.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship, Education, Cote d'Ivoire,

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Introduction

In West Africa, Côte d'Ivoire is positioned as a country conducive to business creation. According to recent data, the rate of business creation has seen a significant increase in recent years. In 2022, more than 15,000 new businesses were created in Côte d'Ivoire, an increase of 10% compared to the previous year. Côte d'Ivoire attractiveness as an investment destination has strengthened, with an increase in foreign direct investment (FDI) in the country. According to statistics, FDI reached nearly US\$1.2 billion in 2021, representing an increase of 15% from the previous year. However, it is clear that despite all these investments and efforts by the Ivorian government to improve the living conditions of Ivorians, the rate of youth unemployment remains growing. A national employment policy based on three pillars, namely business development, training and the governance of employment instruments. Training is therefore a very important aspect in the employment and job creation process. Once the investments have been made, it would be important to take a look at the introduction of entrepreneurship among young people and in academic training with a view to having

convincing results. The development of the culture of entrepreneurship would be a good step towards reducing the unemployment rate. According to Zaki et al., (2016), Productive entrepreneurship is generally considered conducive to economic growth by exploiting new business opportunities and creating new jobs. Indeed, to have productive entrepreneurship, entrepreneurs should have training in entrepreneurship. Educating students about innovation and entrepreneurship can help them develop real-world skills to lead extraordinary lives in this fast-paced and evolving world.

1. Entrepreneurship Education

Entrepreneurship is often considered a personal characteristic, which depends on personal factors and contextual factors. However, according to Saraiva (2016) practice and various facts show that entrepreneurship is ultimately a skill that can be taught and learned. Entrepreneurial education consists of developing the capacity of learners to create social, cultural or economic value. Also, it enables learners through experiences throughout the training to think critically and creatively, undertake complex problem solving, negotiate, communicate and lead. All these elements contribute to the development of the entrepreneurial spirit. Given the impact of entrepreneurship on the unemployment rate, entrepreneurship training is the subject of several research and studies. Also, diversified training in entrepreneurship is offered at all levels of education, from primary or secondary schools to higher university programs. Instilling notions of entrepreneurship is becoming more and more important in the face of the various challenges of the moment.

According to Miço H, Cungu J. (2023), entrepreneurship education is a recent field of education. This area is directly related to small businesses. Indeed, entrepreneurship education helps improve students' entrepreneurial attitudes and skills. It also allows learners to develop an independent and versatile path by developing the spirit of entrepreneurship. Entrepreneurship education aims to trigger entrepreneurial skills, intentions and attitudes in the learner.

1.1. Entrepreneurship Education in Cote d'Ivoire

Faced with the complexity of the social, economic and ecological challenges that humanity faces, Cote d'Ivoire needs young people who are creative, motivated, enterprising, daring, capable of detecting opportunities, confronting change, adapt and collaborate.

Cote d'Ivoire has in fact pushed the policy of promoting entrepreneurship due to unemployment problems and the inability of the Ivorian State to meet its social policy of State employment in the after independence. Also, always with a view to improving the living conditions of Ivorians, the education reform law of 1995 and the national employment plans (PNE) initiated from 1991 will promote entrepreneurship. as an alternative mode of socio-professional integration for young people.

According to Minichiello (2016), Entrepreneurship education aims to promote two complementary knowledge: the spirit of initiative (or entrepreneurship) potentially dissociated from an entrepreneurial intention and the entrepreneurial spirit, more linked to an entrepreneurship project.

In Cote d'Ivoire, the government has opted for an active communication policy with the aim of encouraging entrepreneurs and developing a spirit of initiative.

To this end, a national forum for entrepreneurship in schools has been established. According to Kam Oleh (2023), this forum aims to encourage entrepreneurship among students by encouraging them to develop their creativity, self-confidence, critical thinking, problem-solving skills and their ability to make informed decisions. This is already a step forward in a country where the culture of entrepreneurship is almost existing. In Côte d'Ivoire, the school entrepreneurship project was introduced into the Ivorian education system in 2015. Its aim is to strengthen the educational mission at school in order to reduce the school dropout rate and contribute to the solving the employability problem. However, it is clear that in practice, actions are not visible.

In higher education in Cote d'Ivoire, entrepreneurship education is much more present, we are witnessing the proliferation of business schools to meet current needs in terms of entrepreneurship.

2. Research Questions

The study examines the situation of entrepreneurship education in Côte d'Ivoire and offers recommendations with a view to having efficient entrepreneurs for the country's economic developments. The research questions for this purpose are:

- What is the situation of entrepreneurship education in Côte d'Ivoire?
- What are the challenges of entrepreneurship education in Côte d'Ivoire?
- What are the recommendations to meet the challenges of entrepreneurship education in Côte d'Ivoire?

3. Theoretical Framework

The objective of teaching entrepreneurship is to create in learners the intention to begin an entrepreneurial adventure. For Ajzen (1991), according to the theory of planned behavior, behaviors are influenced by intentions. These intentions are determined by three factors: attitudes, subjective norms and perceived behavioral control. This theory takes on its meaning in entrepreneurship education. Ajzen, I. (2005) states that the theory of planned behavior assumes that individuals act rationally, based on their attitudes, subjective norms and perceived behavioral control. These factors are not necessarily actively or consciously considered when making a decision, but provide the backdrop to the decision-making process.

Entrepreneurship education also makes it possible to have the necessary human capital that is effective and well trained with a view to having good-yielding businesses. Indeed, having a form of human capital improves the chances of small businesses monitoring (Bruederl et al. 1992). Competent people are a resource for the company and for society in general. According to human capital theory, productivity and efficiency are increased when there is more emphasis on education and training. Becker (1964) argues that, overall, investments in education and training will improve productivity. Through this theory, it is clear that training has a considerable impact on the performance of individuals in society. Entrepreneurial education is often followed by apprenticeships in companies to allow learners to have practical knowledge in the field of entrepreneurship before launching into it. Albert Bandura (1974) in his social cognitive theory states that learning is best through modeling. Indeed, he defines modeling as an acquired behavior that is learned naturally by observing what happens to others in the context of social interactions, experiences and media influences. So, according to this theory, having an attachment or exposure to an environment of entrepreneurs can have a major impact on your attitude and your results as an entrepreneur.

Fig 1 : Impact of entrepreneurship

Conceptual Framework

Source: Researchers (2024)

This figure illustrates the impact of entrepreneurship in society in general. Indeed, it would be important in order to have a satisfactory result to integrate the practice of entrepreneurship training into the standards of Ivorian society. Indeed, entrepreneurship education is a beneficial contribution to society because it makes it possible to instill skills in learners with the aim of having fulfilled and successful entrepreneurs. Indeed, the acquisition of entrepreneurial skills,

concepts and knowledge will further encourage one to engage in entrepreneurial activities. Entrepreneurship education also creates jobs and is a major factor in the development of a nation.

4. Research Methodology

A qualitative research approach was applied in carrying out this research. The impact of entrepreneurial training on the effectiveness of entrepreneurs, the importance of entrepreneurship education and the challenges of entrepreneurial training in Côte d'Ivoire are complex issues fully discussed throughout the course study. The population was made up of entrepreneurs who had acquired entrepreneurial training during their career and entrepreneurs who had not received training. Teachers in entrepreneurial education were also part of this study. The study used quota and purposive sampling techniques, with data collected using in-depth interviews and documentary analysis.

5. Importance of entrepreneurship education in Côte d'Ivoire

In Côte d'Ivoire, the private sector suffers from a lack of innovation and productivity, which contributes to the low level of economic development. In this context, it is important to think about development by introducing entrepreneurship as solutions to the problems of lack of jobs. We must motivate entrepreneurs but even more so encourage them to be trained with a view to obtaining satisfactory results. According to Gazeneuve (1995) education also plays an important role in society because this knowledge is profitable and has an impact on improving living conditions. For Ben Massou, S. (2023), entrepreneurial education gives students the skills necessary to manage the challenges inherent in entrepreneurial activity and exploit market opportunities. Also, entrepreneurship training is a real safety net: it allows you to acquire all the skills necessary to become a good entrepreneur and avoid the pitfalls of business creation mentioned above. In an Ivorian environment where funds are available to support entrepreneurs, training is a way for beginners to acquire knowledge with the aim of minimizing losses and beginner errors.

Entrepreneurial activity results in gains that have an impact on the economy. Therefore, in Côte d'Ivoire, the implementation of entrepreneurial training is an opportunity for the government to develop the economy.

Entrepreneurship education focuses on developing the understanding and ability to pursue entrepreneurial behaviors, skills and attributes in very different contexts.

Entrepreneurship supports economic growth and development through market innovations, and there is a bidirectional relationship between entrepreneurship on the one hand and economic growth and development on the other. This is a boon for Côte d'Ivoire which wants to see its economy developed.

Entrepreneurship is a key driver of economic growth. When individuals take the initiative to start a business, they create new products, services and markets. This leads to increased productivity, innovation and competition, which in turn drives economic growth. As new businesses grow and expand, they generate more revenue and contribute to a country's overall GDP. So, educating the population about entrepreneurship would be a way to encourage development.

6. Challenges of Entrepreneurship Education in Côte d'Ivoire

In Côte d'Ivoire, the challenges facing entrepreneurship training are multiple.

The lack of entrepreneurial culture is a very important obstacle in the challenges facing entrepreneurship training in Ivory Coast. Indeed, without the culture of entrepreneurship, there will be little motivation among young people.

Populations are poorly informed about the contribution of entrepreneurship to their daily lives, making it difficult to invest concretely in it. The very high cost of business schools which provide entrepreneurial training is also a barrier to young Ivorians joining this training. Indeed, entrepreneurship training is provided by private higher education establishments in Ivory Coast. Training in certain private universities in Ivory Coast goes up to approximately 100000000 FCFA/year (\$2500) which is relatively high for the average monthly income per capita in Ivory Coast is \$218, or \$2,620 per capita per year (World Bank, 2022). The training is therefore not accessible to all sections of the

Ivorian population.

Lack of quality training in entrepreneurship. Indeed, education plays a central role in shaping the mindset and skills of future entrepreneurs. The lack of quality training is also another challenge in entrepreneurship education in Côte d'Ivoire.

The lack of orientation of entrepreneurial training according to the needs of Ivorian society. Osuala and Oviawe (2010) defined as an obstacle to entrepreneurship training, the insufficiency of qualified teachers and instructors in the field of entrepreneurship.

7. Recommendations

- Introduction of entrepreneurship concepts from primary school

If the Ivorian government wants to resolve the social problems and challenges in terms of unemployment, entrepreneurship is a significant alternative. To this end, the African Union (2017) is betting on entrepreneurship to meet one of its most important challenges, that of youth employment on the continent. It would therefore be important for African countries, in particular in Cote d'Ivoire, to introduce the concepts of entrepreneurship to learners from primary school. Learners will therefore learn, at the start of their school career, the skills to create value and employment. Teaching entrepreneurship education in primary schools can enable learners to develop the skills and knowledge needed to become successful entrepreneurs. These skills include critical thinking, problem solving, creativity, innovation, communication and teamwork, which are essential to entrepreneurship. According to Abderrahman (2016), the objective of teaching entrepreneurship to students from an early age is to provide them with adequate exposure to entrepreneurial activities with a view to instilling an entrepreneurial spirit in them. In this same vein, Mario (2019) argues that offering after-school entrepreneurship classes to those who have completed high school and want to start a business should be the last step and not the only step in training entrepreneurs. Indeed, the ideal time to start this educational cycle is in primary schools so that their creativity and optimism can be used to maximize the effects. From these observations, we can safely say that teaching entrepreneurship should not be neglected.

- Support entrepreneurs in their efforts

The government should support entrepreneurs and future entrepreneurs in their approach. Grants, loans and tax incentives should be used to provide vital financial support to entrepreneurs. It would also be important to develop incubators, financially accessible to entrepreneurs. Incubators play a determining role in the development of entrepreneurs. To this end, Avantika et al., (2024) affirms that business incubators play a decisive role not only in the launch of startups, but also in supporting the entire entrepreneurial journey.

- Teacher training

The pedagogy for teaching learners must be rethought and teaching teachers. The training of staff involved in teaching and learning entrepreneurship education must have a guideline based on the Ivorian government's entrepreneurship agenda.

- Promote entrepreneurial culture

Reward and recognize successful entrepreneurs, from local to national level, and officially recognize entrepreneurial networks and associations.

This will help motivate all those aspiring to entrepreneurship and create jobs to combat the unemployment that is plaguing Cote d'Ivoire.

Conclusion

Entrepreneurship is a key driver of economic growth, job creation and poverty reduction. It has the potential to be a powerful force for development in Cote d'Ivoire. In Ivory Coast, the culture of entrepreneurship is an aspect that the government should instill in the population in order to motivate more entrepreneurs in Cote d'Ivoire.

The challenge for African entrepreneurs is not just to start, but to grow their business to create more jobs. This is where policymakers and investors have an important role to play in creating an enabling environment for entrepreneurship to flourish. Also, entrepreneurship training should be a very important aspect in the government's education agenda. A skilled and mobile workforce is essential to the economy and offers significant benefits to investors as well as international lending institutions such as the World Bank and the International Monetary Fund (IMF) (Arthur 2023). Training is a means of instilling knowledge in entrepreneurs and future entrepreneurs which will enable them to meet the various challenges they will face in the exercise of their function.

In Cote d'Ivoire, entrepreneurship is thriving. However, the emphasis must be placed on training and supporting the entrepreneur with a view to having efficient entrepreneurship.

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